

Table 1: The detail information of FAITH score calculation for the example in Fig. 1.

Item	Content
Question	A 60 year old man has 6 months of dry cough and increasing shortness of breath A 64 year old man has developed a tremor in both arms over the last 6 months. It is worse on the right. He also reports difficulty sleeping due to restlessness. He appears e motionally flat and has a tremor at rest that is alleviated on movement. Which neurotransmitter is most likely to be deficient?
Options	A. Acetylcholine B. Dopamine C. Glycine D. Norepinephrine (noradrenaline) E. Serotonin
Model Answer	A. Acetylcholine
Model Explanation	The patient’s symptoms, including a tremor in both arms that is worse on the right and difficulty sleeping due to restlessness, are consistent with Parkinson’s disease. Acetylcholine is a neurotransmitter that is often deficient in Parkinson’s disease, contributing to its characteristic motor symptoms. This deficiency, along with the degeneration of dopaminergic neurons in the substantia nigra, is a hallmark of the condition. The patient’s resting tremor that improves with movement further supports this diagnosis. Therefore, the most likely neurotransmitter deficient is acetylcholine.
Clinical Annotation	Parkinson’s disease is due to dopamine deficiency, not acetylcholine. Acetylcholine activity is relatively increased.
Claim 1	Medical claim: (Parkinson’s disease, disease_phenotype_positive, Tremor in both arms) KG matching: “Parkinson’s disease” = “Parkinson disease” “Tremor in both arms” = “Tremor” Knowledge path in PrimeKG: Parkinson disease –(disease_phenotype_positive)–>Tremor FAITH score: 0.9999
Claim 2	Medical claim: (Parkinson’s disease, disease_phenotype_positive, Difficulty sleeping) KG matching: “Parkinson’s disease” = “Parkinson disease” “Difficulty sleeping” = “Sleep disturbance” Knowledge path in PrimeKG: Parkinson disease –(disease_phenotype_positive)–>Sleep disturbance FAITH score: 0.9512
Claim 3	Medical claim: (Parkinson’s disease, disease_phenotype_positive, Restlessness) KG matching: “Parkinson’s disease” = “Parkinson disease” “Restlessness” = “Restlessness” Knowledge path in PrimeKG: Parkinson disease –(disease_phenotype_positive)–>Agitation –(phenotype_phenotype)–>Restlessness FAITH score: 0.8547
Claim 4	Medical claim: (Restlessness, phenotype_phenotype, Difficulty sleeping) KG matching: “Restlessness” = “Restlessness” “Difficulty sleeping” = “Sleep disturbance”

	<p>Knowledge path in PrimeKG: Restlessness $-(\text{phenotype_phenotype}) \rightarrow$ Behavioral abnormality $-(\text{phenotype_phenotype}) \rightarrow$ Sleep disturbance FAITH score: 0.5366</p>
Claim 5	<p>Medical claim: (Parkinson’s disease, disease_chemical_deficient, Acetylcholine) KG matching: “Parkinson’s disease” = “Parkinson disease” “Acetylcholine” = “Acetylcholine” Knowledge path in PrimeKG: Parkinson disease $-(\text{contraindication}) \rightarrow$ Chlorpromazine $-(\text{drug_drug}) \rightarrow$ Acetylcholine FAITH score: -0.7784</p>
Claim 6	<p>Medical claim: (Parkinson’s disease, disease_pathophysiology, Degeneration of dopaminergic neurons) KG matching: “Parkinson’s disease” = “Parkinson disease” “Degeneration of dopaminergic neurons” = “negative regulation of dopaminergic neuron differentiation” Knowledge path in PrimeKG: bronchiectasis $-(\text{disease_protein}) \rightarrow$ SHH $-(\text{bioprocess_protein}) \rightarrow$ negative regulation of dopaminergic neuron differentiation FAITH score: 0.1391</p>
Claim 7	<p>Medical claim: (Degeneration of dopaminergic neurons, nigra—pathophysiology_location, Substantia nigra) KG matching: “Degeneration of dopaminergic neurons” = “negative regulation of dopaminergic neuron differentiation” “Substantia” = “substantia nigra” Knowledge path in PrimeKG: negative regulation of dopaminergic neuron differentiation $-(\text{bioprocess_protein}) \rightarrow$ GSK3B $-(\text{anatomy_protein_present}) \rightarrow$ substantia nigra FAITH score: 0.2766</p>
Claim 8	<p>Medical claim: (Parkinson’s disease, disease_phenotype_positive, Resting tremor) KG matching: “Parkinson’s disease” = “Parkinson disease” “Resting tremor” = “Resting tremor” Knowledge path in PrimeKG: Parkinson disease $-(\text{disease_phenotype_positive}) \rightarrow$ Resting tremor FAITH score: 0.9999</p>
Claim 9	<p>Medical claim: (Resting tremor, phenotype_modifier, Improves with movement) KG matching: “Resting tremor” = “Resting tremor” “Improves with movement” = “movement disorder” Knowledge path in PrimeKG: Resting tremor $-(\text{phenotype_protein}) \rightarrow$ ACHE $-(\text{disease_protein}) \rightarrow$ movement disorder FAITH score: 0.1492</p>
Claim 10	<p>Medical claim: (Dopaminergic neurons, anatomical_location, Substantia nigra) KG matching: “Dopaminergic neurons” = “dopaminergic system” “Substantia nigra” = “substantia nigra” Knowledge path in PrimeKG: dopaminergic system $-(\text{anatomy_anatomy}) \rightarrow$ catecholamine system $-(\text{anatomy_anatomy}) \rightarrow$ molecular system $-(\text{anatomy_anatomy}) \rightarrow$ anatomical system $-(\text{anatomy_protein_present}) \rightarrow$ TSPAN6 $-(\text{anatomy_protein_present}) \rightarrow$ substantia nigra</p>

FAITH score: 0.0274

Whole FAITH score | 0.4199
